

ELECTRIC ARC WELDING OF MAIN PIPELINES**Toirov M.Sh.,***PhD Doctor Navoi State Mining and Technology University***Karimov K.A.,***professor at Tashkent State Technical University named after I. Karimov***Mardonov B.T.***professor Navoi State Mining and Technology University***Abstract**

This article describes the main processing methods, materials and equipment used in welding joints of pipelines in Russia. A comparison of various types of welding performance is given. The methods of non-destructive testing of welds, and promising methods used to eliminate the detected defects.

Keywords: welding, pipeline, repair of pipelines, defectoscopy.

Today, the political and economic importance of the water, chemical and oil and gas complexes for the Republic is difficult to overestimate. The consistent development of the oil and gas industry in the Republic requires constant work to further improve pipeline systems, which are the most effective mode of transport of hydrocarbon and other raw materials and products of their processing. This task is especially relevant in light of a number of major oil and gas pipeline projects being implemented in Uzbekistan. It is known that at the present stage of development of technology for the construction of main pipeline systems, the welded method of connecting sections is the main one. The quality of welding work, along with other influencing factors, is the basis for the further safe operation of the pipeline transport system and its economic efficiency [1].

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, seamless and electric-welded (straight and spiral-seam) steel pipes are currently used for the construction of pipelines, mostly made of low-alloy steels, including thermally and thermochemically hardened grades St20, 09G2S, etc. [2]. According to instructions VSN 2-124-80 and VSN 171-84, pipelines can be laid continuously or in sections. When constructing main pipelines, a sectional laying method is used. Pipes arriving at field welding bases are connected into sections 24-36 m long, after which the sections are transported to the assembly site (route) and welded into strings. All connections on the main threads are made by butt welding; the use of backing rings is not permitted. When connecting pipes into sections, rotary joints are used; when welding sections into strands, non-rotary joints are used [3].

The use of internal centering devices makes it possible to mechanize the assembly operation more fully; in addition, the assembled joint is completely accessible for welding, allowing the root weld to be performed from start to finish without stopping or tacking, which has a positive effect on the quality of the welded joint. When connecting pipeline sections into strings, the use of pipe layers and internal hydraulic centering devices provides a high degree of mechanization of the assembly process, however, welding work is usually performed manually using electric arc welding. When assembling and welding sections at field bases, mechanized lines are used. The sections are assembled using an internal centering device, which is used as a rotator.

The root weld is performed by manual electric arc welding with coated electrodes, semi-automatic welding with flux-cored wire or in a carbon dioxide environment. After completing the root welds, the assembled section is transferred to the second stand, where the joints are finally welded by automatic machines under a layer of flux [3, 4].

According to international researchers conducted by the International Welding Institute, the following traditional arc welding processes will remain the main ones when welding in field conditions: coated electrodes; semi-automatic consumable electrode welding using solid wire and flux-cored wire; submerged arc welding; various options for electric contact welding. For welding main pipelines, special electrodes are used (УОНИ-13/45, type Э42А; УОНИ-13/55К, type Э46А; УОНИ-13/55, type Э50А; ОЗЛ-6, type Э46; type Э50А; type Э50А, etc.), used for welding in any position and providing increased ductility, (mechanical properties of welds), impact strength and resistance of the weld metal to cracking at low temperatures (down to -40 °C).

As welding materials when making rotary joints by welding under a layer of flux, fluxes are used in accordance with ГОСТ 9087-8, АН-348А, АН-60, ОЦ-45, АН-47, АН17-М, as well as ceramic fluxes in accordance with ГОСТ 30756-2001 КВС-19 and АНФ-32 and solid welding wires in accordance with ГОСТ 2246-70 СВ-08ГА, СВ-08Г2А, СВ-10НМА, СВ-10НЮ, СВ-08МХ, СВ-08ГНМ, flux-cored wires are also used like the others (for example ПП -АН24); When forming a root weld, flux-copper pads and movable flux pads are used [5].

In order to increase the productivity of pipeline laying work, the process of welding joints is divided into a number of sequential operations. For example, when making non-rotating pipeline joints, the flow-dissected method has been used, when a team of assemblers and several teams of welders are simultaneously involved. The responsibilities of the assembly team include assembling the joints using an internal centering device. Following the assemblers, each of the welding teams performs its own layer of the seam, and each of the welders performs a certain section of this layer. The free formation of the root weld is ensured by the action

of surface tension forces, therefore the highest productivity among arc welding methods is ensured when welding with solid wire in a protective atmosphere of carbon dioxide.

When welding with coated electrodes, flux-cored wire, under a layer of flux, the volume of the liquid bath is larger due to the molten slag, which means the productivity of these methods is lower. In order to ensure a high rate of welding work, gas-electric welding is performed with two or more arcs. The stability of the formation of weld metal in the lower, vertical and ceiling positions, with uniform penetration of the edges and the formation of a reverse bead on the inner surface of the joint, is achieved by cutting the edges of the joint with a blunting of 2-3 mm (bevel angle 20-25°) and moving the electrode with oscillations across the seam (frequency 1,7-2,0 Hz).

When welding non-rotating joints, the current and welding speed are changed synchronously with the position of the weld pool along the perimeter of the joint. As an example, we can cite the welding mode of a fixed joint in a carbon dioxide environment using solid welding wire of the Sv-08G2S, Sv-10GSMT brands with a diameter of 1,2-1,4 mm. Root weld mode: current 150-220 A, arc voltage 20-23 V, welding speed 15-20 m/h, electrode oscillation amplitude 2,5 mm. Mode for performing a filling or facing seam: current 140-200 A, arc voltage 21-23 V, welding speed 7-15 m/h, electrode oscillation amplitude 10-14 mm. When arc welding in shielding gases, pulsed arc welding gives the best results.

Powerful thyristor and inverter arc power sources make it possible to synchronize the process of transferring metal droplets from the electrode to the weld pool

with current pulses. Inverter technology provides flexibility in arc control and metal behavior as it transfers from the electrode to the molten pool, which improves weld formation conditions, significantly reduces metal spatter and increases welding productivity. Pipeline construction experience shows that the most productive and economical welding method in the field is flash butt welding. Welded joints have the required mechanical properties, while continuous reflow takes 70-90 seconds. The power consumption for this type of welding is 2,0-2,5 kW/cm², and the heated ends of the pipes are upset at a speed of 10-15 mm/s.

TKYC type units are designed for contact flash butt welding. The main unit of stationary installations of the TKYC type is a one-piece assembly and welding head, which has a ring transformer and a mechanism for aligning the abutting edges with a hydraulic drive for clamping, melting and upsetting of pipes. Due to the high cost, the use of resistance welding machines is economically justified with a high concentration of welding volumes. Quality control of welding during pipeline construction includes: certification of welders; certification of technological maps for welding; acceptance criteria based on the results of non-destructive testing and hydraulic tests of joints; monitoring compliance with technological requirements. According to the current regulations VSN 2-124-80 and VSN 171-84, in critical areas, 100% of completed control acceptance joints (KSS) are subjected to control of welds, Fig. No. 1. In other areas, random control is allowed. The main methods of non-destructive testing used in pipeline inspection: magnetographic; ultrasonic; radiation; electromagnetic [6].

Fig.1. Sample for control delivery stick.

An obligatory element of maintenance and repair during the operation of pipelines is to determine the location of a possible defect and the degree of damage to the walls. As a result of the examination, the presence and type of detected defects are determined. On damaged pipeline sections, the following repair methods are used: welding the damaged section using electric arc welding; formation of high-strength fiberglass on the surface of the pipe, which allows you to restore the original load-bearing capacity of the pipe; the use of

overhead reinforcing elements, in which oval-shaped patches are used, with a large perimeter-to-area ratio, increases the leg and depth of penetration of the root of the seam. Methods for repairing pipelines using explosion energy are very promising. On the basis of industrial tests, a complex of technological processes and technical means for their implementation has been created. Technological processes and technical means of using explosion energy during the repair of pipelines have passed the state examination for safety of use, the

technical documentation has been approved by the board of Uzsanokatkontekhnazorat [7].

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